

WE'WORGLK

VA QURLSH

MUAMMOL'ARI

ISSN: 2091-5004

ILMIY TEXNIK JURNAL

№ ISSUE 6 2023 JUNE

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

MODERNIZATION OF THE INDUSTRIAL HOUSING STOCK OF THE CITY OF BUKHARA.

Madrakhimova Zamira Khudoyberdiyeva
Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology. Associate Professor Scientific
Leader

Jumayev Jasurbek Farhodovich
Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, master's degree in building and
construction architecture

Annotation: The total population of Bukhara is more than 270 thousand. 60 percent of them live in high-rise residential buildings. The consistent implementation of structural reforms in accordance with the established strong regulatory and legal framework made it possible to form a completely new system of managing and using the housing fund.

Control of the maintenance of multi-apartment housing stock at an appropriate level is not organized, in many cases the requirements for technical operation of the housing stock and safe living of the population are not established.

Keywords: Bukhara city, population, housing fund, multi-apartment, technical operation,

The standard of living of all layers of the population and the social environment in our society are related to the effective functioning of the housing and communal sector, which is of significant social importance. In the years of independence, large-scale reforms aimed at forming a modern market for the provision of communal services were carried out in Uzbekistan. The consistent implementation of structural reforms in accordance with the created strong legal framework made it possible to form a completely new system of managing and using the housing fund.

Control of the maintenance of the multi-apartment housing stock at an appropriate level is not organized, in many cases the established requirements for the technical operation of the housing stock and the safe living of the population are

allowed to be violated. The rules and deadlines for the repair and restoration of buildings and structures are not being followed, demolition of old houses is not being carried out, the condition of the areas adjacent to multi-family houses does not fully meet sanitary standards, rules and hygiene standards.

The population is not sufficiently provided with quality drinking water and centralized heat supply.

Today, more than 4,000 private housing owners' companies operating in our country provide services to more than 32,400 multi-apartment houses. The scope of construction and reconstruction of houses, primarily on the basis of mortgage loans, is expanding. Despite the continuous growth of the population during the past period, it allowed to increase the level of housing provision per person to 15.2 square meters per person

instead of 12.4 square meters in 1991.

Issues of repair and preservation of historical and cultural monuments, tourism service, city construction and creative works were analyzed. There are more than 800 architectural monuments in the oasis of Bukhara, and 347 ancient architectural monuments have been preserved in the city. On the eve of the jubilee, large-scale construction and construction works were carried out in the city along with beautification and repair of historical monuments. In the years of independence, attention was paid to the cultural heritage, reforms aimed at preserving it were implemented, and the "Historical Center of Bukhara" was created. According to the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on March 3, 2014, "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for the leasing of tangible cultural heritage objects and the areas adjacent to them with investment obligations for their improvement and preservation in the necessary condition" Practical work was carried out to ensure wider and more effective use of the facilities for the purposes of study and tourism, to increase the number of infrastructure and service facilities, to create additional jobs, and to increase the income of the population⁶¹. In 2016, based on the relevant decision of the UNESCO World Heritage Committee, international financial assistance in the amount of 29,000 US dollars was allocated for the development and development of the Management Plan of the historical center of Bukhara. In 2020, the preservation of architectural monuments was raised to a higher level. In order to increase the number of objects visited by tourists to 139 in

the Bukhara region, repair work has begun on 6 mosques, 3 madrasas, 1 noteworthy monument, and 2 complexes. Restoration of "Namozgoh", "Ravgangaron", "Khoja Kalon", "Quy-i Khanaqo", "Kunjak", "Labi Hovuz Qazi Kalon" mosques and "Toshsaroy", "Ko'kaldosh" and "Chuqur" madrasas in Bukhara. funds were allocated for repair works⁶². On December 2, 2016, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted.

Figure 1

In 2017, the construction of new hotels, cultural and entertainment venues, modern residences and a crafts center in the territory of the "Shahristan" market began in Bukhara⁶³. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2017 "On measures to rapidly develop the tourism potential of the city of Bukhara and Bukhara region in 2017-2019" and dated August 16, 2017 "The first priority for the development of the tourism sector in 2018-2019 In accordance with the Decision on Measures, a plan of measures to create favorable conditions for foreign tourists and tourists visiting Bukhara, and to further improve the quality of services provided to them, was

developed. 3 large hotels "Bukhara-palas", "Sahid Zarafshan" and "Orient Star Hotels", which have been idle for more than ten years in the city of Bukhara, were given to investors, and now the reconstruction work has been completed and they have started their operation. The city of Bukhara is famous not only for its architectural monuments, but also for its intangible cultural heritage, its unique national traditions and customs. The traditional festival "Silk and Spices" has been held in Bukhara since 2001. From 2018, the cheerful "Nasriddin Efandi" festival aimed at promoting folklore and comic singing traditions, and from 2019 the "Eastern Foods" festival, dedicated to the presentation of national dishes and sweets, in order to further promote the tourist potential of the region. Bukhara City Day", "Melon Sale", "Bukhara Artisans" festivals are also being organized. In the years of independence, attention was paid to construction plans and construction works in the city of Bukhara. The initial project of the city was developed in 1930 by the architect D.S. Meyerson under the leadership of the institute "Giprogor" in Moscow. Based on this project, it was shown that the "conglomerate" of architectural monuments located in the city center is of historical importance, and at the same time, the architecture of the past will be preserved as a "museum" in the modern development of the city. In 1953, architect N.I. Frenkel conducted research on the organization of protected areas, and based on the results of the research, a recommendation was made to preserve historical settlements. As a result, 35 historical and cultural monuments in

the city were taken under state protection.

In 2019, the project of the master plan for the years 2019-2040 was developed by the Uzshaharzakot LITI of Bukhara city. The natural conditions of the city, the population, the condition of the housing fund, transport and engineering infrastructure, and the ecological situation in the city were taken into account during the design⁶⁹. According to the proposal of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, Islam Karimov and Ibn Sina streets of the city, as well as Hafiz Tanish Bukhari, Jalal Ikrami, Hamza, Sadriddin Ainiy, Ibrahim Mominov, Muhammad Iqbal, Zulfiya Illegally restored two-story buildings in the middle of the street were demolished, and instead of them, the construction of multi-story residential buildings, modern trade and household service complexes, and sports facilities began.

As a result, carrying out large-scale creative works in the city of Bukhara led to the development of the historical city's socio-economic, spiritual-educational, urban planning and architecture. Today, the image of the city of Bukhara has changed radically, and the number of streets with modern buildings is increasing year by year. However, the construction of some residential buildings in the city does not meet modern requirements. In addition, deficiencies in the process of restoration of cultural heritage objects and the lack of restoration experts remain a problem.

References

1. Yunusov, S., & Jumayev, J. (2022). BUXORO SHAHRI INDUSTRIYASINING TURAR-JOY FONDI MODERNIZATSIYASI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(5), 497–501. Извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/2995>
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 7 fevraldagi PF-4947-son «O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida»gi Farmoni lex.uz.
3. R.A. Norov “Qurilish jarayonlari texnologiyasi, qurilishni tashkil etish va rejalashtirish” T– 2019 7-b.
4. Iskandarov Haytboy Xasanboy o‘g‘li “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida qurilish soxasidagi investitsion muhit” "Science and Education" Scientific Journal Volume 1 Issue 3.
5. Xolmurod Baxshullayevich Sayfiyev “Buxoro viloyatidagi tarixiy arxitektura obidalari ob’ektlarining turistik marshrutlari va infratuzilmalarini ishlab chiqish” Scientific Progress VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 7 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1601 302-b.
6. <http://atlasofurbanexpansion.org/cities/view/Bukhara>
7. Madiev, FM; Xudayberdiev, A; "Restoration is not labor, it is science." Science and Education, 2, 4, 157-162, 2021, "SCIENCE AND EDUCATION» SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL ISSN 2181-0842 VOLUME 2, ISSUE 4 ..."

